

Pregnancy Outcome at Advanced Maternal Age (≥35 Years): A Prospective Cohort Study

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Abstract

Background: Advanced maternal age (AMA), which is defined as becoming pregnant at the age of 35 or older, is becoming more common due to people getting married later in life, pursuing higher education and advances in reproductive technologies. AMA has been associated with heightened risks of maternal and perinatal complications, though findings remain inconsistent across populations.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the maternal and neonatal outcomes associated with advanced maternal age among pregnant women in Basrah, Iraq.

Method: A prospective cohort study was conducted from December 2011 to September 2012, involving 531 pregnant women in their second trimester attending antenatal clinics in four primary health care centers in Basrah. Women aged ≥35 years (n=180) comprised the study group, while those aged 20–29 years (n=351) served as controls. Data were collected through structured interviews and follow-up through the postnatal period. Statistical analysis included chi-square tests, logistic regression, and relative risk calculations.

Results: AMA was significantly and independently associated with gestational hypertension (RR=9.86), preeclampsia (RR=5.33), gestational diabetes (RR=15.2), cesarean delivery (RR=1.96 elective; 1.69 emergency), postpartum fever (RR=2.9), postpartum hemorrhage (RR=1.96), low birth weight (RR=2.59), macrosomia (RR=5.44), and NICU admission (RR=2.91). No significant association was found with antepartum hemorrhage, preterm birth, or ICU admission. All births were live, with only one neonatal death recorded.

Conclusion: Advanced maternal age significantly increases the risk of several maternal and neonatal complications. However, with appropriate antenatal care, pregnancy at AMA can still result in favorable outcomes, as perinatal mortality was rare.

Introduction

Advanced maternal age (AMA), defined as maternal age of 35 years or older at the estimated date of delivery, has become increasingly prevalent due to delayed family planning, rising educational attainment, later marriages, and the availability of assisted reproductive technologies (ART) [1,25]. As a result, the live birth rate among women aged 35 years and above has risen significantly, with a notable increase in first pregnancies in this age group. Historically, healthcare

providers have classified pregnancies at AMA as high risk due to a perceived increase in maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality [2]. Age-related physiological changes such as reduced cardiovascular reserve, preexisting medical conditions, and diminished physical adaptability may contribute to these adverse outcomes [3]. However, other contributing factors, including genetics, prenatal care, nutrition, and socioeconomic background, are also significant determinants of pregnancy outcome [2,4].

More Information

How to cite this article:

Abdulkareem MB, Hasan MA, Abbood HS. Pregnancy Outcome at Advanced Maternal Age (≥35 Years): A Prospective Cohort Study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(3):179-85.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).27

Keywords:

Pregnancy, outcome, advanced, maternal age, cohort study.

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Several studies report no increased risks when AMA pregnancies are managed at tertiary care centers, largely due to advances in medical care and chronic disease management [3]. Nonetheless, AMA has been associated with a number of complications. These include gestational hypertension, where older maternal age correlates with increased incidence, potentially due to vascular changes or related comorbidities [5,6]. Similarly, gestational diabetes mellitus is significantly more common in older mothers, likely due to insulin resistance and declining β -cell function with age [6,7]. Complications such as miscarriage, ectopic pregnancy, and antepartum hemorrhage also increase with age [7]. Increased maternal age is linked to a higher incidence of multiple pregnancies, partly due to higher use of ART [8], and a greater likelihood of cesarean delivery due to muscular deterioration and fetal malpresentation [6,7]. Postpartum hemorrhage, congenital anomalies, and stillbirth are also more frequently observed in AMA pregnancies [7,9]. While some studies support these associations, others report no significant relationship [10]. Key contributors to neonatal morbidity and mortality, preterm birth and low birth weight have shown inconsistent associations with AMA. Some studies highlight significant risks, especially in women over 40 years, while others found no such link [7,11]. Despite extensive literature, the findings on AMA outcomes remain conflicting [12]. In light of the absence of localised research in Basra, the present study was conducted to investigate the relationship between AMA and adverse maternal and foetal outcomes in this specific population.

Method

A cohort follow-up study was conducted in Basrah city center from December 15, 2011, to September 15, 2012, targeting pregnant women attending antenatal care (ANC) clinics in four systematically selected primary health care (PHC) centers: Al-Razzi, Al-Seef, Al-Ribaath, and Al-Nahtha. The study included two groups: women aged ≥ 35 years (study group) and women aged 20–29 years (control group). Both groups were in their

second trimester at enrolment. For each woman in the study group, two age-matched controls were selected from the same center and on the same visit day. A total of 552 women were initially enrolled (184 in the study group and 368 in the control group), with 531 completing the study after excluding those lost to follow-up (2.2% and 4.6%, respectively). Data were collected through a structured questionnaire in two phases: the first during ANC visits, and the second after delivery during postnatal follow-up or via phone call. Information covered personal, medical, and obstetric history, delivery outcomes, and neonatal status. Some data were verified through ANC cards. Variables were operationally defined for consistency. These included gestational age classifications (term, preterm, post-term) [11], delivery modes, causes for cesarean sections [9], maternal complications such as gestational hypertension and diabetes [13], bleeding [14], postpartum fever [15], and neonatal outcomes like low birth weight (LBW), NICU admission, and early neonatal death [11]. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 17.0. Chi-square, Fisher’s exact test, and logistic regression were employed, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant. Relative risks (RR) were computed using standard epidemiological formulas. Official approval was granted by the Basrah Directorate General of Health prior to the study’s commencement.

Results

Occupation: The majority of women in both groups were housewives — 84.8% in the study group and 90.2% in the control group. Education: Educational levels were similar between the groups, with the highest proportion in both having only primary education. Housing: Most women owned their houses (64.7% in the study group and 66.3% in the control group). A small percentage lived in illegal housing (2.7% vs. 2.2%). Consanguinity: No significant difference in consanguineous marriage was found ($P > 0.05$). Around 34.8% of people in the study group and 40.5% of people in the control group were married to relatives (see Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Study and Control Groups

Variables	Study group Age (≥ 35) years		Control group Age (20-29) years	
	No.	%	No.	%
Occupation				
House wife	156	84.8	332	90.2
Employed/students	28	15.2	36	9.8
$\chi^2=3.535$ Df=1 P=0.060				
Education	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate/read & write	16	8.7	44	12.0
Primary	66	35.9	132	35.9
intermediate	46	25.0	77	20.9
Secondary	21	11.4	37	10.0
High education	35	19.0	78	21.2

X ² =2.613		Df=4		P=0.624	
House ownership	No.	%	No.	%	
<i>Owned</i>	119	64.7	244	66.3	
<i>Rented</i>	60	32.6	116	31.5	
<i>Illegal</i>	5	2.7	8	2.2	
X ² =0.249		Df=2		P=0.883	
Consanguinity	No.	%	No.	%	
<i>Yes</i>	64	34.8	149	40.5	
<i>No</i>	120	65.2	219	59.5	
X ² =1.686		Df=1		P=0.194	
Total	184	100.0	368	100.0	

A significantly higher percentage of women in the study group had a history of hypertension (5.4%) compared to the control group (0.5%) (P=0.0001). No significant differences were found between groups regarding diabetes mellitus or other chronic diseases. The study group had significantly higher rates of abortion (34.8% vs. 20.7%), gestational hypertension (10.9% vs. 3.0%), and caesarean delivery (17.9% vs. 11.7%). Gestational

diabetes, stillbirth, preterm delivery, and Rh incompatibility showed no significant group differences. No statistical difference was observed in congenital anomalies, ectopic pregnancy, or toxoplasmosis. Other outcomes like antepartum bleeding, transfusion during pregnancy, and neonatal death were also similar between groups (Table 2).

Table 2: Past Medical History of the Study and Control Groups, Past Obstetric History of the Study and Control Groups

Variable	Study group (n=184)	Control group (n=368)	P value
Variable	NO.	NO.	P value
Hypertension	10	2	0.0001*
Diabetes mellitus	4	2	0.099*
Other chronic diseases	7	11	0.611
Variable	No.	No.	P value
Abortion	64	76	0.0001
Still birth	8	6	0.056
Preterm delivery	3	10	0.320*
Gestational hypertension	20	11	0.0001
Gestational diabetes	2	0	0.111*
Rh incompatibility	9	11	0.260
Congenital anomalies	2	4	0.681*
Cesarean section	33	43	0.045
Others	9	11	0.260

There was a significant difference in parity between the study and control groups (P=0.0001). A significantly higher proportion of women in the study group than in the control group were of high parity (21.7% and 0.8%, respectively). The reverse was true for nulliparous women (9.8% and 32.4% of the study and the control groups respectively). The incidence rates of gestational hypertension, preeclampsia and gestational diabetes mellitus, were significantly higher in the study group in

comparison with the rates in the control group (21.7% vs. 2.2%, 2.2% vs. 0.3 and 7.6% vs. 0.5% respectively; RR=9.86, 5.33 and 15.2 respectively; P=0.0001, 0.045 and 0.0001 respectively). However, there was no significant association between advanced maternal age and APH, or other conditions like oligohydramnios, polyhydramnios, premature uterine contraction, blood transfusion, and deep vein thrombosis (see Table 3).

Table 3: Characteristics of the Present Pregnancy of the Study and Control Groups. Pregnancy Complications for the Study and Control Groups

Variable	Study group (No. %)	Control group (No. %)	Statistical Test
Parity			
0	18 (9.8%)	119 (32.4%)	

1-4	126 (68.5%)	246 (66.8%)		
≥5	40 (21.7%)	3 (0.8%)	X ² =94.133, df=2, P=0.0001	
Type of gestation				
Singleton	182 (98.9%)	364 (98.9%)	Fisher's exact test, P=0.681	
Multiple	2 (1.1%)	4 (1.1%)		
Variable	Study group (No. %)	Control group (No. %)	RR	P value
Gestational Hypertension	40 (22.9%)	8 (2.2%)	9.86	0.0001
Preeclampsia	4 (2.2%)	1 (0.3%)	5.33	0.045*
Gestational Diabetes Mellitus	14 (7.8%)	2 (0.5%)	15.2	0.0001*
APH	4 (2.2%)	5 (1.4%)	1.57	0.349*
Others	11 (6.0%)	11 (3.0%)	2.0	0.091

Most women in both groups delivered in hospitals (87.8% in the study group, 89.7% in the control group), with no significant difference (P=0.492). Home deliveries occurred in 12.2% of the study group and 10.3% of the control group. Caesarean section rates were higher in the study group (31.1%) compared to the control group (17.0%). Elective CS was 16.7% vs. 8.5%, and emergency CS was 14.4% vs. 8.5% in the

study and control groups, respectively. The association between advanced maternal age and CS was significant, with RR of 1.96 for elective and 1.69 for emergency CS (P=0.001). Hypertension was a significantly more common indication for both elective (P=0.05) and emergency CS (P=0.015) in the study group (see Table 4).

Table 4: Place and Mode of Delivery for the Study and Control Groups, Indications for Elective Caesarean Section for the Study and Control Groups, Indications for Emergency Caesarean Section for the Study and Control Groups

Variable	Study group (No. %)	Control group (No. %)	RR / P value
Place of delivery			X ² =0.473, df=1, P=0.492
Home	22 (12.2%)	36 (10.3%)	
Hospital	158 (87.8%)	315 (89.7%)	
Mode of delivery			X ² =13.857, df=2, P=0.001
Vaginal delivery	124 (68.9%)	291 (83.0%)	
Elective CS	30 (16.7%)	30 (8.5%)	RR=1.96
Emergency CS	26 (14.4%)	30 (8.5%)	RR=1.69
Elective CS Indications			P values
Previous scar	14 (46.6%)	20 (66.6%)	0.118
CPD	2 (6.7%)	3 (10.0%)	0.500*
Malpresentation	2 (6.7%)	2 (6.7%)	0.694*
Hypertension	6 (20.0%)	1 (3.3%)	0.050*
Diabetes mellitus	2 (6.7%)	2 (6.7%)	0.694*
Others	4 (13.3%)	2 (6.7%)	0.335*
Emergency CS Indications			P values
Failure to progress & fetal distress	11 (42.3%)	19 (63.4%)	0.116
Hypertension (Emerg.)	7 (26.9%)	1 (3.3%)	0.015*
Others (Emerg.)	8 (30.8%)	10 (33.3%)	0.838

The incidence of postpartum fever was significantly higher in the study group (≥35 years) at **6.7%**, compared to **2.3%** in the control group (<35 years) (RR = 2.9, P = 0.012). No significant associations were observed between advanced maternal age and postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) (RR = 1.96, P = 0.103), need for blood transfusion, or ICU admission (RR = 1.57, P = 0.363).

All deliveries resulted in live births with no gross fetal anomalies observed. Preterm birth occurred more in the study group (5.0%) compared to controls (3.7%), though the association with maternal age was not statistically significant (RR = 1.35, P = 0.478). Post-term delivery was slightly higher in the control group (1.7%) versus none in the study group.

Low birth weight (LBW), very low birth weight (VLBW), and macrosomia were all significantly more frequent in the study group:

- LBW: **18.9%** vs **7.3%**
- VLBW: **2.4%** vs **0.3%**
- Macrosomia: **4.9%** vs **0.9%**

Admissions to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) were also significantly higher among neonates of older

mothers (19.8% vs. 6.8%; relative risk (RR) = 2.91; p = 0.0001), primarily due to prematurity, respiratory issues, hypoglycaemia, jaundice and seizures.

There was one early neonatal death in the study group, yielding a neonatal mortality rate of **5.5 per 1000 live births**, attributed to prematurity and respiratory complications (see Table 5).

Table 5: Combined Maternal and Neonatal Outcomes

Variable	Study Group (n)	Study Group (%)	Control Group (n)	Control Group (%)	RR	P value
PPH	11	6.1	11	3.1	1.96	0.103
Postpartum fever	12	6.7	8	2.3	2.9	0.012
Other complications	4	2.2	5	1.4	1.57	0.363
Preterm delivery	9	5.0	13	3.7	1.35	0.478
LBW	31	18.9	24	7.3	2.59	0.0001
VLBW	4	2.4	1	0.3	8.0	0.044
Macrosomia	8	4.9	3	0.9	5.44	0.008
NICU admission	36	19.8	24	6.8	2.91	0.0001
NICU: Hypoglycemia	9	25.0	2	8.3		0.095
NICU: LBW/Prematurity	24	66.7	12	50.0		0.197
NICU: Respiratory problems	13	36.1	14	58.3		0.09
NICU: Jaundice	2	5.6	1	4.2		0.65
NICU: Fit	0	0.0	1	4.2		0.4

In order to determine if the adverse outcomes of pregnancy were independently associated with advanced maternal age, logistic regression analyses for different outcomes were carried out. The results indicated that gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, delivery by caesarean section,

postpartum fever, PPH, LBW and macrosomia were significantly and independently related to maternal age. While no significant association was found between advanced maternal age and antepartum hemorrhage and preterm delivery (see Table 6).

Table 6: Obstetric complications by maternal age: Adjusted Models*

Outcome	Age ≥35 vs. referent group (20-29years)	
	Adjusted OR (95%CI)	P value
Gestational Hypertension	9.915 (4.429 – 22.195)	0.0001
Preeclampsia	13.180 (1.254 – 138.548)	0.032
Gestational diabetes	7.581 (1.857 – 30.950)	0.005
Caesarean delivery	1.868 (1.174 – 2.972)	0.008
LBW	2.958 (1.592 – 5.496)	0.001
Macrosomia	6.301 (1.622 – 24.471)	0.008
Postpartum fever	3.056 (1.179 – 7.921)	0.022
PPH	2.431 (1.006 – 5.872)	0.048
APH	2.982 (0.784 – 11.346)	0.109
Preterm delivery	1.629 (0.664 – 3.994)	0.287

Note: *Adjusted models controlled for the effects of education, parity, past medical history and past obstetric history

Discussion

In recent years, the trend of delayed childbearing has become increasingly common due to educational, career, marital, and personal factors [16]. Despite the natural decline in fertility with age, assisted

reproductive technologies (ART) have enabled many women aged ≥35 years to conceive successfully [17]. This prospective cohort study assessed the maternal and neonatal outcomes associated with advanced maternal age (AMA) compared to younger women aged

20–29 years. The study design allowed for direct incidence rate comparison and risk calculation, with minimal loss to follow-up (2.2% in the study group and 4.6% in the control), reducing the likelihood of bias [18]. However, since women were enrolled in the second trimester, the study could not assess first-trimester complications like miscarriage. Outcomes were primarily based on documented evidence, helping minimize observer bias. A significant association was found between AMA and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and gestational diabetes mellitus, corroborating findings from study in Iran [19]. This relationship is likely due to reduced vascular compliance and increased insulin resistance with age [20]. While some studies noted no significant increase in gestational hypertension for women ≥ 40 years [23], most evidence supports the observed association. Although previous studies have linked AMA to an increased risk of antepartum hemorrhage (APH), especially due to placenta previa and abruption [7,19,21], the present study did not find a statistically significant association. This could be attributed to the smaller number of women over 40 years and the study's limited sample size. Caesarean section rates were significantly higher among the study group, reflecting findings from multiple studies [6,7,21,22]. The increased rate is largely explained by previous cesarean deliveries and complications such as hypertension, diabetes, and fetal malpresentation. Similarly, postpartum complications, particularly postpartum hemorrhage and puerperal fever, were significantly more common in older women, echoing findings by Yogeve et al. and the Kirkuk study [9,21]. The higher incidence of fever may also be attributed to the elevated rate of cesarean deliveries and associated infections [23]. Preterm birth did not show a significant association with AMA in this study, aligning with findings from and Iran [22]. However, other studies reported increased preterm births in women ≥ 40 years, possibly due to related obstetric complications [7,19,21]. Neonates born to older mothers were more likely to have low birth weight (LBW) or macrosomia. LBW is commonly linked to hypertensive disorders, while macrosomia is associated with maternal diabetes [24]. These findings are consistent with previous reports [19,21,22]. NICU admission was significantly more frequent in the AMA group, driven by complications like LBW, hypoglycemia, respiratory distress, and jaundice—findings supported by studies from Iran and Bahrain [21,22]. Though only one early neonatal death occurred and no major congenital anomalies were detected, the short follow-up period (one week) may have limited identification of subtler or delayed neonatal outcomes. Studies show mixed findings on the association between AMA and neonatal death or anomalies, with some indicating increased risk

in women ≥ 40 years, especially among nulliparas [7,19,21,22].

Conclusion

Advanced maternal age (≥ 35 years) was identified as a significant independent risk factor for several adverse outcomes, including gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes mellitus, cesarean delivery, postpartum fever, postpartum hemorrhage, low birth weight, and macrosomia. However, it was not associated with increased risk of antepartum hemorrhage, preterm birth, or the need for blood transfusion and ICU admission. Despite these complications, pregnancies in women of advanced maternal age may still be considered relatively safe, as perinatal death was rare.

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